

Deposition of ZnO containing coatings on Ti6Al4V alloy surface using micro-arc oxidation to achieve antimicrobial properties

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Abstract. Micro-Arc Oxidation (MAO) using a pulsed unipolar source of voltage is a unique method of surface treatment technology. The MAO method was used to enhance the bioactivity of the titanium alloy surface and to incorporate of ZnO into the MAO coating, to achieve antibacterial properties. The Ti6Al4V alloy coating layer with ZnO was characterised using scanning electron microscopy and an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer. Biocompatibility was studied using Human mesenchymal stem cells. Metabolic activity was assessed using an MTS assay. Although the surface coating containing ZnO could be a promising modification of the Ti6Al4V alloy, the pilot test proved it to be relatively highly cytotoxic to a human mesenchymal stem cell, a key cell type involved in the connective tissue healing process.

1. Introduction

The Micro-Arc Oxidation (MAO) technique, also known as plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO), involves the physical deposition of a protective oxide coating on titanium, magnesium, zirconium, and aluminium metal alloys to enhance their surface properties. Ti6Al4V is the most commonly used alloy in the aerospace, shipbuilding, sports industries, automotive, and medical industries due to its excellent mechanical properties, high strength, corrosion resistance, fatigue and high temperature stability [1]. The Ti6Al4V alloy, which is predominantly composed of 90% titanium, 6% aluminium, and 4% vanadium, stands out due to its combination of a high strength-to-weight ratio, a high Young's modulus, biocompatibility, high fracture toughness, and high corrosion resistance in biofluids [1, 2, 3]. Except for its superior properties, Ti6Al4V has poor thermal conductivity, low strain hardening, unstable coefficient of friction, low abrasion and wear resistance, which makes Ti6Al4V alloy susceptible to poor tribological behaviour [2,3,4]. Setting appropriate MAO process conditions enables the reduction of pores, which in turn contributes to increasing the wear resistance and stability of the coefficient of friction [2].

The growth mechanism of the oxide layer, thickness, roughness, mechanical and corrosion properties, and chemical composition of MAO coatings can be significantly influenced by process

conditions and electrolyte composition [5]. Therefore, MAO technology is a suitable method for developing bioactive coatings on implant surfaces. The physical and chemical properties of surfaces can influence the most important processes for the successful application of any medical implants: cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation [6].

Both titanium and the Ti6Al4V alloy lack antibacterial properties and as foreign materials in organism they attract bacterial adhesion. This is connected to the implant-associated infection caused by microorganisms that attach themselves to the surface of the material [6]. Therefore, implants should have both great osteogenic properties and antibacterial activity [7]. An effective way to prevent bacterial infection is to incorporate antibacterial agents into the surface of MAO coatings to enhance their antibacterial properties.

Silver [8], copper, zinc, and their metal oxides nanoparticles [6,9] are known for their antimicrobial effectiveness. Compared with silver and copper, zinc is an important trace element for humans, playing a diverse role in many biological functions [10], exhibits superior antibacterial behaviour and better cytocompatibility and biosafety. Yu et al. reported that zinc-containing MAO coatings exhibited favourable physical properties, biocompatibility, and angiogenic and osteogenic potential, in addition to stable zinc release [11].

In present paper, MAO technology was used to prepare a coating containing Zn on the surface of the Ti6Al4V alloy to achieve the antibacterial properties for use in orthopaedic and trauma implants.

2. Experimental

2.1 Sample preparation

Coatings were prepared using a pilot MAO unit equipped with unipolar switching power (DEHOR-elspec. Litvínov s.r.o., Czech Republic) with a pulse unit (Fig. 1).

The MAO pilot unit consists of stirred degreased bath (A) containing 1M NaOH solution (45°C; 5 min), stirred rinsing baths (B, D and F) with distilled water (conductivity <10 μ S/cm; 1 min), pickling bath (C) containing mixtures of 20 wt.% HNO₃ and 2 wt.% HF (25°C; 1 min), stirred rinsing bath (E) with a counter electrode (electrolyte; pH \geq 12). Bath is equipped with a water cooling jacket to maintain the temperature of electrolyte at 30°C. The last bath (G) is rinsing bath with distilled water (conductivity <10 μ S/cm; 1 min).

Figure 1. The MAO pilot unit.

The surface of the Ti6Al4V alloy samples with a diameter of 15 mm and a thickness 2.6 mm were unified through a combination of mechanical and chemical treatments. The Ti6Al4V alloy

surface was degreased in the inlet bath (A) and then rinsed in bath (B). The oxides present on the surface were removed in bath (C), which contained a mixture of acids, and then the surface was rinsed (D). The MAO process was carried out in an electrolyte bath (E) containing mixture of $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Na_3PO_4 , EDTA and $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Zn}$ at a voltage of 450 V for 15 minutes, with temperature control. The interaction of the Ti6Al4V alloy with the electrolyte is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The interaction of Ti6Al4V alloy with electrolyte.

2.2 Surface analysis

The surface of the coating was studied using a Scanning Electron Microscope JEOL JSM-7610F Plus (JEOL, Japan) equipped with an autoemission gun as the electron source. The elemental composition of the coating was determined by an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX, Ultim Max 65 mm², Oxford Instruments).

2.3 Cell culture

Samples of the studied materials were put in sterile 24-well tissue culture plates (TPP, Switzerland) human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) were used to test the biocompatibility of the studied material. The cells were seeded in density 10,000 cells/cm² and then cultivated for 1, 3, and 7 days in MSCM culture medium supplemented with 10% of FBS (ScienCell, USA).

2.4 Metabolic test

The MTS assay (CellTiter 96® – Promega, USA) was used to assess the metabolic activity of the human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) cultivated on the studied materials. The MTS test was done on days 1, 3, and 7 after cell seeding from triplicates. The MSCM medium was washed off the cells using phosphate-buffered saline (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and DMEM medium with 10% FBS and without phenol red was mixed 5:1 with the MTS reagent, added to the cell culture and let to react for 2h. The absorbance was measured at 490nm and 650nm (as background) using a VersaMax spectrometer.

2.5. Fluorescence staining and microscopy.

The cells cultivated on TSC-Zn and control materials were fixed using 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 min, permeabilized using 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and subsequently stained for cell nuclei using DAPI dye (Merck, USA) and for F-actin using phalloidin conjugated with AlexaFluor 568 (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). The fluorescence images were acquired on an Olympus IX71 microscope, obj. ×10.

3. Results and discussion

The SEM image (Figure 3) shows micro-pores on the surface of the MAO coating. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of Ti, Al and V in the Ti6Al4V alloy, as well as Zn, P, Ca and Sr, which were deposited by the MAO coating from the electrolyte. The MAO coating layer contains 6.1 wt.% of ZnO.

Figure 3. The SEM image and EDX analysis of MAO coating on the Ti6Al4V alloy.

The results from cell metabolic activity measurements (Figure 4) suggest that the hMSCs adhere to all the measured surfaces in similar numbers (measurement from day 1). However, the measurement from day 3 already shows relatively high cytotoxicity of the TSC-Zn sample. The metabolic activity is reduced to 50% of the activity on Ti6Al4V and PS samples. This tendency is even more pronounced on day 7. The metabolic activity further grows exponentially on the Ti6Al4V and PS samples; however, the activity on the TSC-Zn sample is still close to day 3.

Figure 4. Cell metabolic activity of hMSCs measured by MTS test, the cells were cultivated on TSC-Zn, Ti6Al4V alloy (TiAlV), and tissue culture polystyrene (PS) for 1, 3, and 7 days. Data are presented as mean \pm SD.

The microscopy images confirm the MTS measurement results. On the first day, cells adhere in similar numbers on ZnO (TSC-Zn) and control materials (Figure 5). However, we can already observe that cells spread less on the TSC-Zn sample. On the Ti6Al4V alloy (TiAlV) the hMSCs grew similarly to tissue culture polystyrene (PS), and they reached full confluence on day 7. While the cells on the MAO coating of Ti6Al4V with ZnO (TSC-Zn) hardly grew and remained rounded, they do not spread into an elongated or polygonal shape. We can only speculate what caused the high

cytotoxicity of the coating. The cytotoxic effect of ZnO is dependent on its physical form. The study of Neykova et al. shows that the toxicity of precipitated ZnO crystals is dependent on their size and shape [12]. However, ZnO nanoparticles have a larger specific surface area and are open for chemical reactions. Zn²⁺ ions can produce ROS, leading to oxidative stress or damage to DNA [13]. Zn²⁺ itself can compete with other important bivalent ions in the cells, disrupting cellular ion homeostasis and enzymatic functions. It can also influence important signalling pathways like MAPK, NF- κ B, PI3K/Akt [14].

Figure 5. Microscopy images of hMSCs cultivated on TSC-Zn, TiAlV alloy, and tissue culture polystyrene (PS) for 1, 3, and 7 days. Nuclei are counterstained by DAPI (blue), and actin filaments are stained with phalloidin-AF568 (red).

4. Conclusion

Micro arc oxidation technology and a Zn-containing electrolyte were successfully used to incorporate Zn into the coating of Ti6Al4V alloy. This study proved that the MAO-produced ZnO coating of the Ti6Al4V surface is relatively highly cytotoxic to hMSCs, a key cell type involved in connective tissue healing processes. Therefore, the conditions of the MAO process and the composition of the electrolyte will be the subjects of further investigation.

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Data availability

The data presented in this study are available on Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15743667>.

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